

1. TED system

1.1. System description

The TED device is an advanced technological device developed by 4Sec Ltd, equipped with an accelerometer, gyroscope, and GPS capable of detecting a high number of samples per second related to gravitational acceleration and angular velocity on all three axes (x, y, and z), as well as position data. The device has been designed to adapt to the biological variability of each individual. In this sense, it is fully programmable, and its performance is optimized for each individual. The process of adaptation and improvement of the quality of produced information is continuous. The collected data is sent to the Cloud collection system, both continuously (monitoring of the function of interest) and on occasions of events inserted into the monitoring plan (such as falls or the risk of falling). The data collected on the Cloud system are then processed by Machine Learning systems capable of extracting knowledge and learning elements from the device data, using the most modern machine learning techniques.

1.2. Technical specifications

1.2.1. Design features

The design features essentially encompass two main aspects:

- Functional (acquisition parameters, sensors, power supply, etc.)
- Ergonomics and wearability (shape, weight, IP rating, material compatibility, etc.)

1.2.2. Functional features

Functional features pertain to a series of non-vital parameters acquired through sensors installed on the electronic boards. An important aspect of patient monitoring relates to the localization and control of mobility and stability to detect potential falls and potentially risky situations. To achieve this, the device is equipped with a GPS module, an accelerometer, and a vectorial gyroscope; the sensors can also detect phenomena such as tremors and hyperkinesias. A buzzer for auditory notifications + LED is present.

The electrical autonomy exceeds 5 hours and can reach up to 72 hours depending on usage conditions. The device includes a rechargeable lithium polymer battery with a voltage of 3.7V and a capacity of 2000 mAh, nominally corresponding to a maximum total energy of 7.4 Wh. The charge duration depends heavily on how the hardware resources of the device are managed via the firmware. The device is equipped with a connector for SIM card and SD card. Battery charging is done via a micro USB connector.

1.2.3. Ergonomics and wearability

To facilitate wearability, the device is positioned using a plastic support attached to the patient's belt with sliding insertion. Applying the device to the patient's body is quick and simple.

1.2.4. System architecture

The system architecture is based on the ESP32-WROVER-E module, which combines MCU WiFi-BT-BLE functionalities. The following table outlines the device characteristics.

MCU Module:

Categories	Items	Specifications
Certification	RF certification	FCC/CE-RED/SRRC
Test	Reliability	HTOL/HTSL/uHAST/TCT/ESD
Wi-Fi	Protocols	802.11 b/g/n (802.11n up to 150 Mbps) A-MPDU and A-MSDU aggregation and 0.4 μ s guard interval support
	Frequency range	2412 ~ 2484 MHz
Bluetooth	Protocols	Bluetooth v4.2 BR/EDR and BLE specification
	Radio	NZIF receiver with -97 dBm sensitivity
		Class-1, class-2 and class-3 transmitter
		AFH
Audio	CVSD and SBC	
Hardware	Module interfaces	SD card, UART, SPI, SDIO, I ² C, LED PWM, Motor PWM, I ² S, IR, pulse counter, GPIO, capacitive touch sensor, ADC, DAC, Two-Wire Automotive Interface (TWA ^I ®, compatible with ISO11898-1)
	On-chip sensor	Hall sensor
	Integrated crystal	40 MHz crystal
	Integrated SPI flash	4 MB
	Integrated PSRAM	8 MB
	Operating voltage/Power supply	3.0 V ~ 3.6 V
	Minimum current delivered by power supply	500 mA
	Recommended operating temperature range	-40 °C ~ 85 °C
	Package size	(18.00±0.15) mm × (31.40±0.15) mm × (3.30±0.15) mm
Moisture sensitivity level (MSL)	Level 3	

Figure 1: TED technical specifications

LTE Communication Module:

The communication module used is the A7672xx produced by SIMCom, with the following technical specifications (European Version A7672E).

Product	A7672S	A7672E	A7672SA
Form Factor	LCC+LGA	LCC+LGA	LCC+LGA
Dimensions(mm)	24.0*24.0*2.4	24.0*24.0*2.4	24.0*24.0*2.4
Frequency Bands	LTE-FDD	B1/B3/B5/B8	B1/B2/B3/B4/B5/B7/B8/B28/B66
	LTE-TDD	B34/B38/B39/B40/B41	
	GSM	900/1800MHz	900/1800MHz
Temperature	-40°C ~ +85°C	-40°C ~ +85°C	-40°C ~ +85°C
Electrical Features			
Supply Voltage(V)	3.4~ 4.2	3.4~ 4.2	3.4~ 4.2
Power	LTE TBD	TBD	TBD
Consumption (mA)	GSM,BS_PA_MFRMS=2 TBD	TBD	TBD
Data Transfer			
LTE(Mbps)	10(DL)/5(UL)	10(DL)/5(UL)	10(DL)/5(UL)
GPRS/EDGE(Kbps)	236.8(DL)/236.8(UL)	236.8(DL)/236.8(UL)	236.8(DL)/236.8(UL)
Software Features			
Protocol	TCP/IP/IPV4/IPV6/Multi-PDP/FTP/FTPS /HTTP/HTTPS/DNS	TCP/IP/IPV4/IPV6/Multi-PDP/FTP/FTPS /HTTP/HTTPS/DNS	TCP/IP/IPV4/IPV6/Multi-PDP/FTP/FTPS /HTTP/HTTPS/DNS
TLS	•	•	•
MQTT	•	•	•
File System	•	•	•
Audio Record/Play	0	0	0
TTS	•	•	•
LBS	•	•	•
FOTA	•	•	•
Android RIL	Android 5.0/6.0/7.0/8.0/9.0	Android 5.0/6.0/7.0/8.0/9.0	Android 5.0/6.0/7.0/8.0/9.0
USB Driver	Microsoft Windows 7/8/10 Linux/Android	Microsoft Windows 7/8/10 Linux/Android	Microsoft Windows 7/8/10 Linux/Android
WWAN (RNDIS)	•	•	•
ECM	•	•	•
Embedded AT	0	0	0
Firmware Upgrade	USB/FOTA	USB/FOTA	USB/FOTA
Interfaces			
SIM Card	1.8V/3.0V	1.8V/3.0V	1.8V/3.0V
UART	•	•	•
USB	•	•	•
PCM	0	0	0
ADC	•	•	•
GPIO	•	•	•
I2C	•	•	•
GNSS	0	0	0
BLE	0	0	0
Certification			
Certification		CE-RED*/RoHS*/ REACH*	Anatel*/RoHS*/ REACH*

Figure 2: technical specifications of the LTE communication module.

NOTES:

The WiFi-BT-BLE and LTE A7672E MCU modules used in the device individually comply with CE directives on Radiofrequency.

Accelerometer and Gyroscope Modules:

The gyroscope/accelerometer is based on the LSM6DS3TR-C module produced by ST.

Symbol	Parameter	Test conditions	Min.	Typ. ⁽¹⁾	Max.	Unit
LA_FS	Linear acceleration measurement range			±2		g
				±4		
				±8		
				±16		
G_FS	Angular rate measurement range			±125		dps
				±250		
				±500		
				±1000		
				±2000		
LA_So	Linear acceleration sensitivity ⁽²⁾	FS = ±2		0.061		mg/LSB
		FS = ±4		0.122		
		FS = ±8		0.244		
		FS = ±16		0.488		
G_So	Angular rate sensitivity ⁽²⁾	FS = ±125		4.375		mdps/LSB
		FS = ±250		8.75		
		FS = ±500		17.50		
		FS = ±1000		35		
		FS = ±2000		70		
LA_SoDr	Linear acceleration sensitivity change vs. temperature ⁽³⁾	from -40° to +85°		±0.01		%/°C
G_SoDr	Angular rate sensitivity change vs. temperature ⁽³⁾	from -40° to +85°		±0.007		%/°C
LA_TyOff	Linear acceleration zero-g level offset accuracy ⁽⁴⁾			±40		mg
G_TyOff	Angular rate zero-rate level ⁽³⁾			±3		dps
LA_OffDr	Linear acceleration zero-g level change vs. temperature ⁽³⁾			±0.5		mg/°C
G_OffDr	Angular rate typical zero-rate level change vs. temperature ⁽³⁾			±0.05		dps/°C
Rn	Rate noise density in high-performance mode ⁽⁵⁾			5		mdps/√Hz
RnRMS	Gyroscope RMS noise in normal/low-power mode ⁽⁶⁾			75		mdps

Figure 3: range of the sensors embedded in the TED device.

Figure 4: symbolic view of the inertial module.

Figure 5: overall Electronic Board View:

Schematic Diagrams:

PROJECT:	4sec Tracker
DRAWING TITLE:	IN
DRAWN BY:	
SHEET: 3	OF 3
STATUS:	
DATE:	05/01/23
REVISION:	

F

E

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C

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PROJECT: 4sec Tracker	
DRAWING TITLE: Power	
DRAWN BY:	
SHEET: 1 OF 3	STATUS:
DATE: 05/01/23	REVISION:

1

2

3

4

1.2.5. Plastic case

The casing is made of PA12 using 3D microfusion printing technology. The following figures represent the device in various views. The casing has an IP52 protection rating.

Figure 6: plastic case models.

The following figure illustrates the solution for the wearability of the device.

Figure 7: smart badge overview

Figure 8: exploded components

1.2.6. Device Dimensions:

Summary of tech specifications:

Processor	esp32
Connectivity	4G, WiFi, Bluetooth, BLE
Sensors	Accelerometro, Giroscopio, GPS
Memroy	448KB ROM, 536KB SRAM (slot for SD card available)
Battery capacity	3700 mAh
Weight	136 g